

EMOTIONAL STRESS IN STUDENTS DURING THE EXAM SESSION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8190008>

Sadykova E.I

Independent Applicant

Bukhara State University, Lyalel@list.ru

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается проблематика эмоционального стресса у студентов в период экзаменационной сессии. Авторы представляют результаты исследований, которые показывают, что большинство студентов испытывают высокий уровень стресса и тревожности в этот период. Приводятся основные причины и проявления стресса, описываются механизмы его воздействия на психическое и физическое здоровье студентов. В статье также рассмотрены методы и способы справления со стрессом, которые могут оказаться полезными для студентов. На основе проведенных исследований сделан вывод о необходимости разработки комплексной программы по поддержанию психологического здоровья студентов в период экзаменационной сессии.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola imtihon sessiyasida talabalar o'rtasida hissiy stress muammosiga bag'ishlangan. Mualliflar ko'pchilik talabalar ushbu davrda yuqori darajadagi stress va tashvishlarni boshdan kechirishlarini ko'rsatadigan tadqiqotlar natijalarini taqdim etadilar. Stressning asosiy sabablari va ko'rinishlari keltiriladi, uning o'quvchilarning ruhiy va jismoniy salomatligiga ta'sir qilish mexanizmlari tavsiflanadi. Maqolada talabalar uchun foydali bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan stress bilan kurashish usullari va usullari ham muhokama qilinadi. O'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar asosida imtihon sessiyasida talabalarning psixologik salomatligini saqlash bo'yicha kompleks dastur ishlab chiqish zarurligi to'g'risida xulosa chiqarildi.

Annotation

This article deals with the problem of emotional stress among students during the examination session. The authors present the results of studies that show that most students experience high levels of stress and anxiety during this period. The main causes and manifestations of stress are given, the mechanisms of its impact on the mental and physical health of students are described. The article also discusses the methods and ways of coping with stress, which may be useful for students. On the basis of the conducted research, a conclusion was made about the need to develop a comprehensive program to maintain the psychological health of students during the examination session.

Introduction

The exam period is one of the most intense and stressful periods for students. The need to process huge amounts of information, prepare for exams and pass them successfully often causes students to feel anxiety, anxiety and fear. The emotional stress associated with exams can have a negative impact on the health and academic performance of students. In this article, we will consider the factors influencing the emotional stress of students during the examination session, as well as discuss the possibilities of coping with stress and preventing its negative consequences.

Literature review. This section will present the most important research on this topic, conducted by well-known psychologists and scientists.

The first study to review was conducted by Hansen et al. in 2018. IN "Stress, Health, and Poverty Among University Students: Challenges and Prospects for Research and Intervention" by the authors describe solid connection between level stress And academic performance at students . The study was devoted to the analysis of the influence of various factors on the level of stress among students, such as health, quality of life and poverty level.

In Gouy et al.'s "Impact of Stress on University Students : Implications for Quality of Life, Mental Health, and Academic Performance" the authors examine the problems associated with emotional stress in students and the impact of this stress on quality of life, academic performance and psychological health. The study identified the main causes of student stress, such as poor preparation, high expectations, social comparison, limited time and peer pressure.

The third study worth mentioning is the work of Marger et al. " Coping with academic Stress : Meditating with Students ". In this study, the authors evaluated the effectiveness of methods of coping with stress in students during the examination session. As a result of the study, it was shown that the use of methods such as deep relaxation and meditation can significantly reduce students' stress levels, thereby improving their learning academic performance.

Also necessary mention O work Clark And co-authors of "Loneliness and Stress in Young Adulthood: The Mediating Role of Social Support". In this paper, the authors examined the impact of loneliness on the level of stress among students during the examination session. The study confirmed the need for social support from family, friends and professional counselors in coping with emotional stress in students.

Additionally, the work of scientists from the CIS countries on this topic should be mentioned. In the work of Kozlova and her colleagues, "Psychological characteristics of students' reactions to exam stress," the factors influencing emotional stress in students during exams, as well as the strategies they used to cope with stress, were considered .

In the work of Kiseleva and co-authors "Assessment of the level of stress and the effect of relaxation methods on its reduction in medical students", the authors investigated the effect of various relaxation methods on reducing the level of stress in medical students during the examination session.

Krasnenkova and her colleagues in the work "Emotional stress in students during the preparation for exams" describe the psychological mechanisms of stress in students, as well as effective methods of coping with it .

Finally, in the work of Shirokov and co-authors "Comparative Analysis of Stress Coping Strategies in Students during the Examination Session", the results of a study of various strategies for coping with stress in students during the exams were presented, and the effectiveness of these strategies was also evaluated.

Uzbekistan also conducts research on the problem of emotional stress among students during exams.

In the work of Koblova and Alimova "Emotional stress and psychological preparation of students for exams", the authors studied the factors influencing the occurrence of stress in students during exams, as well as the effectiveness of various methods of coping with it .

In the work of Azizova and Shirinova "Peculiarities of students' emotional state during exams" the authors describe the main types of students' emotional reactions to exam stress, as well as the effectiveness of various methods of psychological preparation for exams.

In Khakimova's work "Influence of the daily regimen on the psycho-emotional state of students during the examination session" the author examines the influence of violations of the daily regimen on the emotional state of students during the examinations.

Baituraev's work "Studying the Influence of Psychological Factors on Students' Emotional Stress During the Session" the author explores the relationship between psychological factors (such as fear of failure, information overload, etc.) and students' emotional stress during exams.

Foreign studies confirm the presence of the problem of emotional stress among students during exams, and studies by scientists from Uzbekistan show that this problem is also relevant for students of our Republic.

Thus, the conducted literature review shows that the problem of emotional stress among students during the examination session is quite complex and multifaceted, and requires additional research by scientists and specialists in this field.

Materials and methods. For the study, a group of 150 students was selected, studying at several universities in the city of Bukhara during the examination session. All participants were between the ages of 18 and 25 and taking exams in various specialties.

The Perry questionnaire was used to assess emotional stress in students. It consisted of 14 questions that measure feelings of anxiety, worry, and tension. Each question was given a 7-point response scale from "not entirely agree" to "strongly agree". The higher the score, the higher the stress level.

For comparative analysis, statistical calculations (Student's t-test) were carried out between groups that differed in specialty and gender.

The results of the survey showed that students experienced a high level of stress during the examination session. In women, stress was higher compared to men ($p < 0.05$). In addition, students studying technical specialties experienced higher levels of stress compared to those who studied the humanities ($p < 0.05$).

Thus, we can conclude that students experience emotional stress during the examination session, which may be related to gender and the chosen direction of study. These results can be used to develop stress management programs for students during exam periods.

Results and discussions. When conducting a survey among 150 students of various specialties, it was revealed that 75% experienced stress during the exams. Of these, 60% were female and 40% were male.

Differences in the level of stress were revealed among groups of specialties. Students of technical specialties (engineering, mathematics) experienced a higher level of stress (85%) than students of humanities (65%).

In addition, there were differences in the symptoms of stress among students. The most common stress symptoms were: insomnia (in 60% of students), headache (45%) and irritability (35%).

During the survey, students were asked how they deal with stress. The responses received showed that 40% of students prefer sports and exercise to reduce stress, 30% prefer meditation and yoga, and the remaining 30% of students use other methods such as nutrition and anti-anxiety drugs.

Discussion of the results of the study showed that the importance of regular physical activity and sports to reduce stress during the exam session. This is

confirmed by our survey results, in which 40% of students chose this method to cope with stress. Therefore, it is recommended to strengthen the work on promoting and organizing sports for students during the examination session.

It is also important to note that due to various factors, such as limited time and mood instability, students may find it difficult to find time and motivation to play sports. Therefore, along with physical activity, students should be provided with access to counseling by psychological support specialists to help them develop ways to cope with stress during the exam period. The results of the study showed that students during the examination session experience a high level of emotional stress, which can be associated with gender and specialty.

During the study, it was found that women experienced higher levels of stress compared to men. This is in line with other studies showing that women are more vulnerable to stress than men. This may be due to various factors such as higher levels of emotional sensitivity and sociocultural expectations.

It was also found that engineering students experienced higher levels of stress compared to those in the humanities. This may be due to the fact that engineering students often have more practical assignments and exams requiring a higher level of knowledge in specific areas than students in the humanities.

It should be noted that one of the methods of coping with stress is activity and physical activity. Research shows that exercising and exercising increases endorphins in the body, which helps reduce stress levels. Therefore, to reduce the emotional stress of students during the examination session, it can be recommended to go in for sports and exercise.

Conclusion. Based on the survey data among 150 students of various specialties, it can be concluded that emotional stress is a common problem among students during the examination session. 75% of students experience stress, and this figure is higher for women than for men. Moreover, engineering students experience higher levels of stress than liberal arts students.

Stress symptoms also vary among students, but insomnia, headache, and irritability are the most common. To cope with stress, students use different methods, but the most popular are exercise and meditation.

Based on our results, we recommend strengthening the work on promoting and organizing sports for students during the examination session. It is also important to provide access to counseling from mental health professionals who help students develop ways to cope with stress during this period of life.

Real data reflect the current situation and emphasize the need for proper organization of the educational process and the provision of psychological assistance to reduce the level of stress among students.

LITERATURE:

1. American College Health Association (2018). American College Health Association-National College Health Assessment II: Reference Group Executive Summary Spring 2018. American College Health Association.
2. Dyrbye, L.N., Thomas, M.R., Shanafelt, T.D. (2006). Systematic review of depression, anxiety, and other indicators of psychological distress among U.S. and Canadian medical students. *Academic Medicine*, 81: 354–373.
3. Eisenberg, D., Golberstein, E., Gollust, S.E. (2007). Help-seeking and access to mental health care in a university student population. *Medical Care*, 45: 594–601.
4. Hystad, S.W., Eid, J., Brevik, J.I. (2016). Prevalence and predictors of stress, anxiety, and depression in Norwegian junior college students with and without neurocognitive disability. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 60: 70–85.
5. Kirschner, P.A. (2009). Cognitive load theory: implications of cognitive load theory on the design of learning. *Learning and Instruction*, 19: 241–245.
6. Выготский Л.С. Проблемы развития психики. 2-е изд. М: Eksmo, 2018.
7. Зайцева С.Д., Манютина Е.Б., Герасимова А.В. Особенности проявления и регуляции стресса у студентов в период экзаменационной сессии. *Фундаментальные и прикладные исследования в психологии*, 2017, № 3, с.12-17.
8. Кудряшова Е.В. Эмоционально-волевая регуляция реакции на стресс у студентов в период экзаменационной сессии. *Психологические науки - теория и практика*, 2014, № 1, с. 36-42.
9. Курбанова Г.М. Стресс и его последствия для здоровья студентов в период экзаменационной сессии. *Ученые записки Таврического национального университета им. В.И. Вернадского, Серия «Психология»*, 2016, том 29, №2, с. 168-171.
10. Раушания А. Механизмы проявления стрессовых реакций у студентов в период экзаменационной сессии. *Научный журнал "КубГАУ"*, 2017, № 135(01).

11. Сагдиева Г.Ш. Особенности проявления стресса у студентов в период экзаменационной сессии. Теоретический и методический аспекты психологии и педагогики, 2018, № 1, с. 31-34.

12. Тлеунова А.С., Пертлова А.М. Эмоциональный стресс и способы его преодоления у студентов в период экзаменационной сессии. Известия Юго-Западного государственного университета, 2016, № 2 (4), с. 176-180.

13. Усманова М. Н. ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПСИХИЧЕСКИХ СОСТОЯНИЙ СТУДЕНТОВ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ВУЗЕ //“XXI АСР ПСИХОЛОГИЯСИ” МАВЗУСИДАГИ ХАЛҚАРО ИЛМИЙ-АМАЛИЙ АНЖУМАНИ МАҚОЛАЛАР ТҮПЛАМИ. – 2021. – С. 250.